

COOU Undergraduate Students' Exposure to Online Reports on Messi's 2023 Ballon D'Or Victory and Their Perception of Ronaldo's Reaction to the Reports

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Abstract

Sports is one of the activities that bind people of different races together. During the 2022 world cup, many countries participated and records of the players were kept. In October, 2023, the winner of the Ballon d'or was announced to be Lionel Messi. That announcement triggered some reactions especially on the internet more especially the reaction from Cristiano Ronaldo who happened to be one of Messi's sports rivals. Audience perception of Ronaldo's reaction is the main thrust of this research. The objectives of the study are to find out respondents' extent of exposure to online reports about Messi's Ballon D'Or victory, their level of knowledge about Ronaldo's reaction and their perception of the reaction. Anchored on Uses and gratifications, and social cognitive theories, the work used survey research method to source data from a population of 15, 786 students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Taro Yamane's formula was used to get a sample size of 390 and purposive sampling technique was used to distribute the copies of the questionnaire to the respondents. Findings revealed a high level of awareness of reports on Messi's Ballon D'Or victory and that the respondents are highly aware of Ronaldo's reaction to the reports under study though greater majority of them perceive Ronaldo's reaction as a sign of envy on his own part. It was recommended that FIFA should make honest effort to ensure that their decisions are worthwhile so as to avoid such reactions that may discredit the body in the future.

Keywords: Exposure, Online reports, Ballon D'or victory, Perception, Reaction.

Introduction

Sports is a major aspect of national life across the globe. This is underscored by the participation of every country in sporting activities, as different countries contest to dominate others in different sporting activities (Ibagere, 2015). Sports has provided the media with various and predictable audiences that are attractive to advertisers both in the USA and around the globe (Kumari, 2019). The revenue from sports reportage is a great source of income for the different media outlets, particularly the newspaper, television, and specialty magazines (Woods, 2006). Sports has become a major social factor, helping the people to resist bad habits and the flows of “cheap culture” products (Redner, 2004, in Skinner, Smith & Swanson, 2018). Sports has also become a powerful political tool, helping to increase the patriotism of the nation and its unity, and motivates the leadership and social responsibility of citizens (Seippel et al., 2018).

People with sporting experience think that sports helped them gain the features of strong personality, such as self-confidence, and the ability to plan and realize the set goals (Shamir & Eilam, 2005, in Fox & Lindwall, 2014). It also helps people to develop the ability of sacrificing themselves to achieve the goal. One sporting experience gained in the youth strongly influences the behavior of people in their whole lives. It allows people to realize that in critical situations they can rely only on themselves. All of the personal features developed by them in the period of sporting make the main factor, allowing them to stay alive in the modern world and in extreme situations (Pierre, Hofinger & Simon, 2016). Since sports has a social basis, it is in the centre of the social science research. Sporting activities promote the development of interrelations and communication between people of different tribes, continents and races. One objective evaluation of the importance of sports requires not only the knowledge of the form and content of sporting activities, but also the awareness of the social needs, motives and relationships, making the foundation of the formation of personalities, social groups, communities and nations. Sports is not homogeneous; it has various parts, including political, economic, social, cultural and spiritual.

Sports includes many activities involving single contestants and hundreds of simultaneous participants, as well as teams. It is essential to have a general, scientifically sound definition and to clearly understand the description of activities that could be considered as sports. Moreover, the phenomenon of sports fandom has been identified as a significant factor in the social development of secondary school students' identification with a favorite sports team or athlete, and has been linked to increased social connectedness, group cohesion and the development of shared values among adolescents (Wann, 2018). According to a study by Wann and Grieve (2005), watching sports with peers can create a shared social identity and a sense of belonging among individuals. This experience enhances social connections, as fans gather to support their favorite teams or athletes. The emotional investment and collective celebration or disappointment during televised sporting events foster bonds and cultivate a strong community spirit. Sports fans are people who have strong emotional attachments to their favorite team, athlete or sports. They are loyal, enthusiastic and spend a larger amount of their time and resources consuming the teams' products; whether obtaining tickets to games, buying jersey of their favorite players, to gathering with loved ones to view the game on TV, sports fans are passionate and enthusiastic with sports (Kim et al., 2020).

Socialization process involves the means of developing sports fandom by which certain determinants that influence one's identity as a fan are known as socialization agents (Wann & James, 2019). According to Kim et al. (2020), the media have had far reaching effect on the world of sports. Modern day sports fans can utilize their phones, tablets or laptops to check

updates from other games, join with fantasy sports and/or take part in gambling activities with various ways to consume sports media. Fans can consume sports contents from multiple media platforms all at once (Lewis & Gantz, 2019). One distinctive aspect of sports fandom is in its sharing-nature as sports is in fact a widely consumed content within the mass media.

Consuming sports has become a large part of American culture over recent decades. This is because of the improvement in technology, which allows persons to view and follow sports from any part of the world and this has led to generation of funds from all-rounds; this has resulted in a big boom in the sports industry, strengthening its position as a fundamental principle of American society (Mastromartino, Chou, & Zhang, 2018). It has to be noted that sports fans can facilitate their identity through exposure to sporting activities on TV (cinema), exposure to sports stories on the mass media or the social media, or even belong to a particular sports club, as the case may be.

During the 2023 international football award, there was a breaking news that Lionel Messi has secured the win for the Ballon D'Or award adding to the multiples of this same kind of award the superstar had secured over the years against his world opponent and contender to that particular award, Cristiano Ronaldo. When this news came to the Instagram, Rolando dropped a laughing emoji-reaction to the report. Thus, the study emanates from the angle of sports fandom and sports message circulation on social media. The essence is to evaluate the extent of knowledge of, and audience perception of the reaction to the story under review.

Statement of Problem

In the recent years, the world of football has been dominated by the rivalry between Lionel Messi and Cristiano Ronaldo, two of the greatest players of all time. Their competition for titles and awards, including the prestigious Ballon D'Or, has been extensively covered by the media. The online and mainstream media have given so much prominence to the reports and coverage of this information that has affected sports lovers' perception of the events occurring in the professional lives of these two sports celebrities. In October 2023, Lionel Messi yet again made history as the only footballer with eight Ballon D'Or wins; he fought off the competition with other nominees like Erling Hanland and former Paris Saint-Germain team-mate Kylian Mbappe as well as 26 others to win the award, but Cristiano Ronaldo was not nominated for the award at all. The circulated information on the internet especially as reported by journalist – Joseph Zucker, showed Ronaldo's reaction to the information of Messi securing the win away from his counterparts. However, little is known about COOU undergraduate students' knowledge about the online reports on Messi's Ballon D'Or victory in 2023 and their perception of Ronaldo's reaction to the reports.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives that guided the study:

- To assess the extent of exposure to online reports on Lionel Messi's Ballon D'Or victory by the respondents.
- To ascertain the audience level of knowledge of Cristiano Ronaldo's reaction to the online reports on Lionel Messi's Ballon D'Or Victory.
- To investigate respondents' perception of Cristiano Ronaldo's reaction to the online reports on Lionel Messi's Ballon D'Or victory.
- To analyze the factors that influence respondents' exposure to online reports on sports, specifically Lionel Messi's Ballon D'Or victory with regards to Cristiano Ronaldo's reaction.

- To examine whether there is a significant relationship between Ronaldo's reaction to the online reports on Messi's Ballon D'Or victory and the respondents' aggregate position.

Theoretical Framework

Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT)

Uses and gratification, otherwise called utility theory was propounded by Blumler, Katz and Gurevitch in 1974. The theory seeks to explain the functions a particular medium plays for the audience. UGT investigates what people do with a communication content instead of what the content does to them; hence communication need, communication content selection, communication content breeding and communication need actualization of the individual. UGT claims that the people use the media for their own benefit rather than vice versa; in other words the influence of the media is based on what people permit it to be (Asemah, 2011). For Folarin (1998) UGT sees the audience as actively controlling the result because they selectively choose, attend to, appraise and absorb the media messages on the basis of their needs, beliefs etc. The focus was shifted from media production and transmission functions to the media consumption function.

Wimmer and Dominick (2015) argued that UGT takes the view of a media consumer. It examines how individuals use the media and the gratifications they seek and derive from their media behaviors (Agbanu, 2013; Obiakor & Nwabueze, 2019). The theory insists that different people can use the same communication message for different purposes. Hence, people select what they want to watch, read or listen to and various media compete to satisfy their needs. Hence, in context with this study students may seek online reports to stay informed about development in the world of football including major events like Ballon D'Or award; online reports on Messi's victory and Ronaldo's reaction may serve as topics for social interaction and discussion among students. This is in line with the submission of McQuail (1983), that there are different needs for people to engage on a particular media which includes: information, education and entertainment.

The Review

Sports and Sports Communication

Sports is an organized competitive activity that requires robust physical exertion. It is one of such institutions that have their own traditions and values but these normally reflect the patterns in society at large (Adesina, 2012). Wenner (1998) pointed out that sports is a conduct or means through which feelings, values and priorities are communicated. Kumari (2019) cited in Obiakor (2023) believes that sports has availed the media with vast predictable audiences that are attractive to advertisers both in the United States and around the globe. Sports communication refers to the transference of information, messages and stories related to sports through various channels and the media. It encompasses the exchange of information between athletes, coaches, teams, sports organizations, media outlets and the audience, (Ibagere, 2015). Sports communication contributes to promoting sports, engaging fans, shaping public perception and facilitating the flow of information within the sports industry; this involves establishing and maintaining the partnerships with media outlets and sports journalists. Sports organizations, teams and athletes rely on media coverage to reach a wider audience and share their stories. Sports journalism plays a crucial function in sports communication. Journalists report on sports events, interview athletes and coaches, analyze games and provide commentary. Sports

journalists contribute to the storytelling aspect of sports, conveying the narratives, emotions and the import of sporting events to the audience.

Sports communication also encompasses marketing and promotional activities. Sports organizations and teams utilize various communication strategies to promote events, engage fans and build brand loyalty. This includes advertising campaigns, social media engagements, content creation, sponsorships and fan outreach programmes. Sports communication heavily relies on broadcast and digital media platforms to reach a wider audience. Effective sports communication is imperative in building and maintaining positive relationships, enhancing sports experience and sharing public perception of sports entities and events.

Messi's 2023 Ballon D'Or Win: A Brief on Online Reports of/and Ronaldo's Reaction

Lionel Messi an Inter Miran and Argentina striker who played for Paris Saint-Germain during the previous season, captained Argentina to the world cup tournament in 2022, secured his 8th Ballon D'Or victory, an award he won in 2009, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2015, 2019, 2021 and yet again in 2023; thus, crowning him as the king of Ballon D'Or award as he is the most outstanding recipient of the award. Messi fought off the competition from Manchester United's Erling Haaland, former Paris Saint-Germain team mate, Kylian Mbappe as well as 26 other nominees for the award. Lionel Messi in the last season scored the total of 21 goals and 20 assists making him an exceptional player for the reception of this award. It is pivotal to know that Cristiano Ronaldo was never nominated for this particular award in 2023.

Thus, when the news of Messi securing this feat again in 2023 came online through a leaked result announced before the event circulated through a tweet by a highly placed official that is part of the organizing team for the award, Ronaldo reacted to the online report with a laughing emoji under the comment session of the story. What seems to be a minor comment or reaction to news which many lauded as false or not coming from the right source became an internet sensation. Many online keyboard warriors made serials of comments under Ronaldo's laughing emoji-reaction, some calling him jealous, some calling him a rival of the 2023 Ballon D'Or winner, and some applauding him; to all these comments Ronaldo never replied anyone. This summarizes the whole outcome of the online report which sparked a lot of reactions, creating enemies among players and also their fans.

Research Methodology

Survey research method, according to Wimmer and Dominick (2011) makes it easier for large amount of data to be collected with relative ease from various kinds of people as the approach helps the researcher to examine many variables, demographics and the styles, information, attitudes, motives, intention etc., of the population under investigation. The method used for the research was the survey research method. The population in this research consists of the undergraduate students of Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus; the total population as provided by the Institution's Registrar in 2024 is 15,786. According to Nwodu (2017), a sample is part of the entire population that is selected for investigation. It is not usually very possible to cover a large population with a single research endeavor, thus the option is to offer sample. The sample was derived using Taro Yamane's 1973 formula sample size formula stated as follows:

$$S = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

- S = Sample size
 N = Population
 1 = Constant
 e = Error margin = 5%

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \frac{15,786}{1 + 15,786(0.05)^2} \\ &= \frac{15,786}{1 + 15,786 \times 0.0025} \\ &= \frac{15,786}{1 + 39.465} \\ &= \frac{15,786}{40.465} \end{aligned}$$

S = 390(approximately)

Purposive sampling technique was used in carrying out the study; and was used to select the samples. The main goal for using purposive sampling technique is to ensure that the researcher focused on particular characteristics of a population that are of interest, which would best generate answers to research questions. The instrument used in collecting data for this study is the questionnaire which is the primary source of information. It contained multiple choice questions, open-ended and dichotomous response questions.

Data Presentation and Analysis

390 copies of the questionnaire were administered to purposively selected respondents by the researcher. The questionnaire was filled and returned; 5 copies were not properly filled and 4 copies had mutilated answers; thus, making the research to be based on 381 workable returned copies of the questionnaire. This indicates 4.5% mortality rate and on this premise was the presentation of data based.

Answers to Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the extent of exposure to online reports on Lionel Messi's Ballon D'Or victory by the respondents?

Table 1: Respondents' extent of exposure to online reports under study

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Do you know about who secured 2023 Ballon D'Or win?		
Yes	292	77%
No	25	6%
Can't Say	64	17%
Total	381	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Data generated from table 1 above show that greater percentage of the respondents are well aware of Messi's Ballon D'Or victory in 2023; 77% of the respondents said they are aware and exposed to the new story. This shows that the rate of exposure to the story is considerably high.

Research Question Two: What is the audience level of knowledge of Cristiano Ronaldo’s reaction to the online reports of Messi’s Ballon D’Or Victory?

Table 2: Respondents’ knowledge level about Ronaldo’s Reaction to Messi’s Ballon D’Or Victory’s report

Item 5	Frequency	Percentage
Are you aware of Ronaldo’s reaction to Messi’s Ballon D’Or victory’s online report?		
Yes	297	78%
No	29	8%
Can’t Say	55	14%
Total	381	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

Table 2 above indicates that greater majority of the respondents are well aware of Ronaldo’s reaction to the online reports on Messi’s 2023 Ballon D’Or victory with 78% representation.

Research Question Three: What is the respondents’ perception of Cristiano Ronaldo’s reaction to the online reports on Lionel Messi’s Ballon D’Or victory?

Table 3: Respondents’ Perception of Ronaldo’s reaction to Messi’s Victory

Item 6	Frequency	Percentage
How would you describe Ronaldo’s reaction to Messi’s Ballon D’or victory based on what you read online?		
Positive	102	27%
Negative	164	43%
Neutral	86	22%
Not Sure	29	8%
Total	381	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

The data generated from Table 3 above indicate that greater majority of the respondents had negative perception of Ronaldo’s reaction to Messi’s 2023 Ballon D’Or victory with 43% representation. The perception is a result of the rivalry between the two players for years. Most of the respondents have negative feeling of Ronaldo’s reaction to the reports because they see it as envy.

Research Question Four: What are the factors that influence respondents’ exposure to online reports on sports, especially, Lionel Messi’s Ballon D’Or victory with regards to Cristiano Ronaldo’s reaction?

Table 4: Factors influencing respondents’ exposure to online reports on Ronaldo’s reaction to Messi’s Ballon D’Or victory

Item 7	Frequency	Percentage
What factor influences your exposure to the online reports on sports particularly Messi’s Ballon D’Or victory and Ronaldo’s reaction to the reports?		
Personal interest	79	21%

Social media culture	120	31%
Information seeking	56	15%
Peer discussion	52	14%
Others	74	19%
Total	381	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

From the table 4 above, it is evident that social media culture dominated the factors that influence respondents' exposure to online reports on sports especially of Lionel Messi's 2023 Ballon D'Or victory in association to Ronaldo's reaction to the reports with 31% as the representation. Other factors are personal interest, information seeking behavior, peer discussions and interaction and exposure to newspapers on sports, sports magazine, radio and television sports programmes.

Research Question Five: Is there a significant relationship between Ronaldo's reaction to the online reports on Lionel Messi's Ballon D'Or victory and the respondents' aggregate position?

Table 5: Relationship between Ronaldo's reaction & Respondents' aggregate position

Item 11	SA	A	UN	D	SD	Total	X	Decision
Messi is still the best?	125 (625)	109 (436)	44 (132)	78 (156)	25 (25)	1374	3.6	Accepted
C Ronaldo is not just happy; He's envious	112 (560)	102 (408)	101 (303)	52 (104)	14 (14)	1389	3.6	Accepted
But they should have awarded another player; Messi is not the only good player	55 (275)	50 (200)	201 (603)	41 (82)	34 (34)	1194	3.1	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2024.

In Table 5 above, it was found that the relationship between C. Ronaldo's reaction to the online reports of Messi's 2023 Ballon D'Or victory and the respondents' aggregate position is not very significant. From the Likert scale above, it is evident that the decision rule on the issue is that Messi still remains the best despite everything. It was also observed that the aggregate position of the respondents is that C. Ronaldo is only envious of Messi's victory in 2023 even though majority are saying that Messi is not the only good player.

Discussion of Findings

The study is set to ascertain the undergraduate students' exposure to online reports on Messi's Ballon D'Or victory and their perception of Ronaldo's reaction to the reports. In assessing the extent of exposure to online reports of Messi's Ballon D'Or victory by the respondents, it was found that there is a high rate of awareness of the online reports by the respondents as 77% of them are very much exposed to the reports on Messi being the winner of 2023 Ballon D'Or award. It is also credible to know that the greater percentage of the respondents are males, which underscores males' active participation in sports and sports affairs. Furthermore, the finding is also in line with the findings of earlier studies, that social media platforms provide direct access to contents to an unprecedented number of people (Ikegbunam & Obiakor, 2021, in Obiakor, Ikegbunam & Ezeumenwa, 2024; Obiakor, Onwuka & Chinedu, 2024), that social media is one

of the most vibrant means of disseminating information to the masses ((Obiakor, & Ikegbunam, 2021; Obiakor, Ikegbunam & Ezeja, 2024; Obiakor, Okereke & Agbachukwu, 2024; Obiakor, Obiora & Okafor, 2025; Obiakor, 2025), that social media are one of the major sources of information on politics for users (Duru, 2019, in Obiakor & Adikuru, 2024), about a demonstration of the universality of the internet and its permeation ability (Obiakor, Adikuru & Agbakaj, 2022), that WhatsApp is one of the social networking sites where political issues are being discussed everyday by users (Obiakor, Ikegbunam & Ezeaso, 2023) and that the role of the social media in projecting public information to the people is hereby acknowledged (Ikegbunam & Obiakor, 2023). The high exposure to the video may be attributed to the fact that “When audience members in the society distrust the mainstream media, they have a tendency to withdraw from it and turn towards alternative sources (Müller & Schulz, 2021, in Obiakor, 2024). This high level of exposure to the news reports under study depicts an agreement to the fact that vibrant and active media are indispensable tools for the execution of any election (Ezinwa, 2015, in Obiakor, Okelue & Okeke, 2024), in the sense that without access to the full range of information about their world, citizens cannot fulfill their roles, and democracy will wither (Kurfi, 2010, in Obiakor, Okelue & Okeke, 2024). .

The second objective sought to evaluate respondents’ level of knowledge of Ronaldo’s reaction to the online reports on Messi’s Ballon D’Or victory. The respondents said they are well aware of Ronaldo’s reaction to the online reports of Messi’s victory; the reaction came in the form of a laughing emoji posted as comment to the online news of Messi’s victory. The reason of the spark in the spread of this response was the fact that social media are avenues that help in the wide circulation of information mostly gossips, rumors and fake information which spread like wild fire and in this case, what looked like a simple laughing Emoji became an internet sensation because of the kind of individual that made the post. This corroborates the earlier view of Obiakor and Ikegbunam (2021) that the social media provide direct access to contents to an unprecedented number of people.

The Third objective, which sought to assess respondents’ perception of Cristiano Ronaldo’s reaction to Messi’s 2023 Ballon D’Or victory, found that most of the respondents had a negative perception to the reaction of Ronaldo, which they claim the laughing emoji was presenting some kind of disrespect and coming from a rival in the Football games worldwide. However, some respondents said they do not see the reaction as anything meaningful. However, majority of the respondents perceive this reaction as negative.

Ascertaining the factors that influence respondents’ exposure to online reports, factors like; social media culture, personal interest and information spreading made the percentages of 31%, 21% and 15% respectively. This explains the power of the social media in information dissemination and transmission. Social media are agents of prompt and timely discharge of information to all falls of the earth. Thus, the quick dissemination of the information of Ronaldo’s reaction was first recorded on social media and strikes a big credit to its ability for information dispersal across bounders. It has to be noted that several factors according to Obiakor and Nwabueze (2019) could be responsible for exposure to contents such as: information seeking, entertainment, relaxation, diversion, escape, etc. These are certainly based on the position of uses and gratifications theory. Hence, the respondents use the media to gratify themselves and to satisfy their needs.

The last objective evaluated the significant relationship between Cristiano Ronaldo’s reaction to the online reports on Lionel Messi 2023 Ballon D’Or victory and the respondents’ aggregate position on the report. It was found that the respondents believed that the reaction of Ronaldo

does not have any effect on them, as they perceived the reaction as Ronaldo's personal opinion. Thus, it was found after the test using the Likert scale, that C. Ronaldo could be envious of his rivalry, Lionel Messi. It was therefore concluded that Messi is still the best in what he does even though there are other good players there in the field.

Conclusion

Sports carries out socialization tasks and functions through various methods and at different levels. The concept of sports has changed from a source of entertainment and recreation to become an integral part of modern urban life in society. Thus, this study concludes that trends in sports should be noticed and the segmentation of sports and its players should be credibly done as sports fandom is an aspect of the game people do not pay good attention to.

Hence, it was found that the respondents are well exposed to the online reports of Messi's 2023 Ballon D'Or victory and Ronaldo's reaction to the reports. It was also discovered that the respondents have a negative perception of the reaction of Ronaldo to the reports on Messi's award, which was made to ridicule the winner. It was also found that there was no significant relationship between the reaction of Ronaldo on the online report of Messi's 2023 Ballon D'Or victory and the respondents' position on the world best player as the respondents' aggregate position is that Ronaldo is envious of Messi and that Messi is still the best though there are other good players. Therefore, information on sports spanning the walls of the media should be information that will not cause clash but rather improve sports and its related sector for the benefit of man and his environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it therefore recommends thus:

1. That Sports fans should be objective in disseminating information concerning their opponent or rival player in a bad light in such a way that it generates traffic on the Internet, by so doing reduce the rate of misconceptions and misrepresentation of popular players.
2. Sports lovers should embrace the fact that sporting activities are forms of entertainment and socialization not a do-or-die affair that one has to become enemies with their neighbors.
3. Individuals and journalists should be mindful of the type of information they give audience online, mostly in relation to sports and sporting activities.
4. FIFA should also make painstaking efforts to make sure that their decision reflects the true picture of events to avoid reactions of this nature that may discredit the body in the future.
5. Further studies can look at the broadcast media reports of the activities of Messi and C. Ronaldo.

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